

DIMENSIONS OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY ENGAGEMENT BEYOND THE CLASSROOM IN CHALLENGE-BASED LEARNING

P Jimarkon¹

University of Stavanger
Stavanger, Norway

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1613-1406>

M Shaverdi

University of Stavanger
Stavanger, Norway

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9055-5151>

K Dikilitas

University of Stavanger
Stavanger, Norway

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9387-8696>

D Husebø

University of Stavanger
Stavanger, Norway

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¹ *Pattamawan Jimarkon*
P Jimarkon
pattamawan.jimarkon@uis.no

ABSTRACT

The study investigates and reports on the process of engagement in learning through the innovative pedagogical framework – Challenge-based Learning (CBL) – their changing perspectives of learning and their interaction with each other while conducting authentic challenges. This gives way to understanding how learners construct and create meaning out of learning activities, course content and beyond the course objectives. Our mixed method research explores potential impact dimensions of the implementation of challenge based learning on teachers and students. To reveal the potential impact we conducted a focused group interviews with the learners who took part in CBL-integrated lessons and surveyed 68 number of learners who participated in CBL trainings. Our preliminary findings showed that learners undertook news roles by driving their own learning, developing collaborative skills, exploring knowledge to be acquired, and establishing relevance of course content in real contexts which made it meaningful for them to understand. In our presentation, we would like to discuss the implications of CBL implementation on the way higher education can be redesigned by assigning learners a more active role in learning and the engagement that occurred during their learning experiences.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Why Challenge-based learning?

With long-standing experience and successful implementation of problem-based learning (PBL) we propose in this paper that the PBL concept should be taken one step further to strengthen modern European higher education institutions, instigating the pedagogics of challenge-based learning (CBL) together with external stakeholders to foster learner engagement and at the same time building communities by utilizing authentic challenges into the learning process. The difference between PBL and CBL is its strong emphasis on the opportunities to investigating real immediate world problems, the focus on the process and skills that they can then apply beyond the challenge and their education. While PBL's aim is to identify diagnostic problem and the process or working out the solution, CBL addresses "societal challenges" and sustainable societal goals with engineering and business development (Malmqvist et al., 2015).

1.2 Definitions of CBL

Challenge-based learning (CBL) is is 'a multidisciplinary approach that encourages learners to work actively with peers, teachers and stakeholders in society to identify complex challenges, formulate relevant questions and take action for sustainable development' (Rådberg et al. 2020, p. 21). It follows a specific structure, which consists of three main steps: engage, investigate and act (Nichols et al., 2016). Implementation of CBL is recommended in engineering education to allow for combining technology, principles of modern industry, and at the same time skills of communication that are personalized, collaborative and relevant to the needs of society (Conde et al., 2017; Membrillo-Hernández et al., 2021).

1.3 Purpose of the study

This is an inquiry to look into the participation of UiS students partaking the challenge-based learning initiative where the main purpose is to investigate their collaborative work and engagement during the challenge-based learning experience. Beside their weekly regular lessons, all team members which consisted of learners, CBL experts, and external stockholders met and worked on the CBL project once a week over the semester period of three months. They also had several appointments with the stakeholders to collect information for developing their solutions. The challenges developed by the learners were, for example, sustainable digitalisation, food waste, sustainable construction industry, efficient army resources, and efficient warehouses. Each of the three main steps consists of smaller activities, 1) Engage: Big Idea; Essential Questions; The Challenge, 2) Investigate: Guiding Questions Guiding Activities and Resources; Analysis, and 3) Act: Solution; Implementation; Evaluation and Publishing. We can see that these challenges require multidisciplinary efforts from innovative insights from all fields of study.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research objectives

The study employs a questionnaire survey and interviews as the methods of data collection. The aim is to reach the two following research objectives:

- To investigate the learning opportunities and engagement perceived by the CBL learners and teacher assistants during and after the trainings

- To provide pedagogical implications for CBL educators and recommendations for future trainings schemes

2.2 Participants

The first sampling was 68 Bachelor-level students who applied the ECIU challenge-based learning initiative in their project in a 9-ECTS course titled *Information and Technology Management* arranged by the University of Stavanger. They were contacted either through the CBL expert, or their advisor to complete our questionnaire survey. The second sampling consisted of five learners in the team, two students who expressed their interest in partaking in the interview and three teacher assistants.

2.3 Research instruments

A survey The survey took 15 minutes to complete. It had 4 questions that asked for name, department and whether they were an international or a local learner. The survey questions were divided into 2 parts, with the total of 21 questions. It had 5 scales, ranging from 'strongly agree' (5) to 'strongly disagree' (1).

An Interview The interview consists of around 10 questions. It took approximately 45 minutes per interview, and they were recorded. The interview included open-ended questions about their learning experience during the challenge. Because in CBL all participants are considered learners and life-long learners, the teacher assistants were included to be interviewed about the process of learning as well.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Survey results

The results in the first section will be presented in the following seven constructs distributed in the 20 questionnaire items. The learners' perceptions of their CBL learning experiences. The result trends were found to be positive.

Table 1. Average perceptions of learners during the CBL engagement

Clusters	Average
Roles and engagement (defined, changed)	3,27
Feedback	3,4
Knowledge in CBL	3,4
Abilities gained during learning process	3,8
Interpersonal skills and team working	3,96
Knowledge in content of challenge	3,6
Real-world learning	3,3

Most learners reported that their roles during the process of CBL were clearly defined but they were allowed to change the roles during their interaction with other team members. The learners found the feedback they received from their peers, the expert and the stakeholders to be equally helpful. They reported to learn about how to undertake challenge-based learning quite well and that they gained knowledge and skills and abilities from working on the challenge. Their interaction during CBL was reported to increase their interpersonal skills quite a great deal. Their knowledge in the content of the challenge was found to be high but they reported that real-world learning was just above average.

3.2 Interview results

In the following section, we will present the codes, categories and themes of the data base on our interpretation of the extracts. Ultimately, we have found three main themes from the overall analysis as follows.

Theme 1 Cognitive engagement

- Prolonging problem-solving process
'It's still really good to focus at the beginning or not rushing to the to the solution and really looking at the problem from all perspectives and bringing everybody in your team with their backgrounds and their skills too. (TA1)
- Personalising learning experiences
It was also related to public policy and community asset development and my work background is in public policy because I worked in London for over 8 years in public policy rules for UK Health department.' (TA3)
- Relating skills to CBL process
So we have to make a connection between our knowledge or two hour course and our materials with the CBL process and also with the real world companies that we are working with their challenges or problems they're facing. (TA2)
- Constructing own understanding
But in this CBL process, the main thing is no. Now it's not at the starting point. You don't have to think about solution that please first think about your problem. Think about the situation you are in. (TA2)
- Associating with life-long learning
'You have to zoom in your problem. And yeah, then you got the idea where you can implement a solution. OK, yeah, so that's what we also learned with the students and it was a really great experience and we are still learning. (TA3)
- Risktaking
'I wanted to meet and explore a lot of things, so I accepted the challenge. I applied for it and it was really really good because I was only there and actually I didn't know exactly what I'm I was there for, which was really interesting.' (ST2)

We can see that the teacher assistants, as learners, stress that the process of CBL allows for cognitive engagement in different ways. One mentions that it occurred by prolonging the process of finding solution as long as possible, which is the principle of CBL to not jump to the conclusion quickly. In CBL, all members work as a community of practice, to utilize their content knowledge and negotiate through different approaches to find possible solutions. This foster their capabilities of constructing their own understanding beyond classroom.

Theme 2 Social engagement

- Collaboration
'Collaborating there can actually create a real business proposition and online companies and leave it with all these connections and and new knowledge to go and make a difference in the in the real world as well.' (TA1)
- Teamwork
'And all the members and how we just fix, you know the teamwork and CBL really help us to guide us' (ST1)
- Learning environment
'Go with fellow for us, so that's why we were so motivated and the environment of the people actually help us because we were always discussing and adding, having more perspectives and was like the flexibility.' (ST2)

The students and the teacher assistant reported that their contact with group members and external stakeholders brought them with experiences which facilitated their exchange of knowledge about business and real-world issues related to their studies. They reported that their CBL experiences led them to relate to the mechanism of group work and thus utilize this mechanism in this group work.

Theme 3 Connectivist engagement

- Relating theory with real life
'Actually read the materials and the professor actually give us some structure that that that's how the theory says you can do that.' (TA2)
- Putting knowledge into immediate practice
'Organizations are national and local level on data on policy and how they can improve things like for example, waiting times in exit emergency.' (TA1)
- Multidisciplinary collaboration
'really good because it's like a real challenge and we can integrate our knowledge and then get more new perspectives from the others.' (ST1)
- Sense of self-development
'We can integrate our knowledge and then get more new perspectives from the others. And that's what I really want. And I'm here to try to actually expand my mindset as well.' (ST1)

The learners reported the benefits of CBL as to contribute their ability to connect knowledge, skills and practice. They refer to their content subjects and how CBL can help them relate and integrate what they learned in new perspectives with the content interaction and current issues at hand. Potential advantages stem from their CBL experience when it is in combination with other theoretical perspectives (Leijon et al., 2021; Tang & Chow, 2020).

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

These results indicate the importance and value that CBL can help place on the learner's experiences while becoming prospective future workers. Higher education institutions should provide facilities with availabilities of learning environment, materials, technologies and social resources and trainings or teachers to become confident coaches and students to be self-directed learners (Pepin & Kock, 2021). During interaction in class and beyond, the facilitation of learning and opportunities to explore issues are needed. As educators in higher education, we ensure that facilitation of positive engagement, such as these ones are established. Activities that can contribute to learners' sense of trust, collaboration, shared educational achievements should be provided. We have also learned that students should be encouraged to engage in CBL integrated learning in multidimensional manner. With CBL, we can maximise meaningful interaction amongst themselves and with the experts. Interaction with stakeholders can provide real-world context-specific perspectives. This is found to be highly vital especially development of soft skills for students in the fields of hard sciences. Lastly, learning activities such as CBL can provide space for students to reflect critically on the challenge and their own learning.

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